

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

CONTAMINATION OF WHITE STORKS *CICONIA CICONIA* L. DECLINES DUE TO THE REDUCTION OF ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION IN THE ARARAT PLAIN OF ARMENIA

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Abstract

A novelty threat to the White Storks *Ciconia ciconia* was discovered in 2019-2021. The storks were becoming contaminated with an agent of plant oil and/or fish fat nature, which was impeding their flying abilities, causing increased mortality of the young birds. In response, a species-specific strategy and action plan were developed and implemented starting in late 2021, aimed at improving waste management of over 300 producers of fish, chips, and canned food. The monitoring of the White Storks in Ararat Plain of Armenia was conducted in 2019-2021 and continued in 2022-2024 to track the efficiency of the implemented measures. The average percentage of contaminated storks (monitored in 35 villages) grew from 5% in 2019 to 21% in 2020 and to 55% in 2021, followed by a decline of contaminated storks to 34% in 2022, 22% in 2023, and to 19% in 2024. The number of strongly contaminated nestlings (taken as a percentage of all contaminated nestlings) declined from 18% in 2019 to 5% in 2020, then grew up to 24% in 2021, followed by a decline of strongly contaminated storks to 17% in 2022, 16% in 2023, and to 12% in 2024. Continuation of the undertaken measures, development of longer-term measures, and further monitoring of the storks are recommended.

Keywords: White Stork, *Ciconia ciconia*, Contamination, Wetland, Armenia.

Introduction

Wetlands of Armenia represent a significant conservation value, hosting many of breeding and migratory waterbirds protected globally, like White-headed Duck *Oxyura leucocephala*, Ferruginous Pochard *Aythya nyroca*, Common Pochard *Aythya ferina*, Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus*, and nationally, like White-tailed Lapwing *Vanellus leucurus*, Kentish Plover *Anarhynchus alexandrinus*, and Black-winged Stilt *Himantopus himantopus*. The wetlands of Ararat Plain experienced significant decline during the last 70 years from 31,000 ha down to about 2,000 ha (Aghababyan 2011), being also susceptible to pollution from the agriculture (Aghababyan 2011, Aghababyan *et al.* 2013, 2020).

The novelty threat for wetlands of Ararat Plain emerged in Armenia in 2019 thanks to the indicator White Storks *Ciconia nigra* (Aghababyan *et al.* 2022). It was growing stronger and expanding till 2021 (Aghababyan *et al.* 2022), when the joint strategy and

action plan were developed and implemented by the consortium consisting of RA Ministry of Environment, RA Environmental Protection and Mining Inspection Body, BirdLinks Armenia NGO, Protection of Endangered and Endemic Species NGO, and local supporters (Aghababyan *et al.* 2024). Since then, the decrease of pollution of the wetlands and the White Storks was documented in 2022 and 2023 (Aghababyan *et al.* 2024). The current paper aims to document the further dynamics of pollution of the wetlands and the White Storks in 2024 and to conclude on the efficiency of the implemented strategy and action plan.

Study Area

The study area remains the same as in 2019-2023 (Aghababyan *et al.* 2024) being located in the Ararat Plain of Armenia (Figure 1), The area represents a combination of settlements, orchards, vineyards, gardens, wetlands, semideserts, and abandoned salinised arable lands.

Figure 1. Study area (from Aghababyan et al. 2024).

Methods

Although the annual monitoring program of the storks (implemented since 2006) covers Ararat, Armarvir, Aragatsotn, Yerevan, Lori, Shirak, and Vayots Dzor provinces, the focused studies of the contaminated storks were conducted in 2019-2024 and covered only the Ararat Plain. Data collection involved 23 expeditions lasting a total of 28 days and covering 42 locations. Results of the survey of 2019-2023 have already been published (Aghababyan et al. 2022, 2024) and are now supplemented with additional data from 2024. Some of the previous data are repeated here for the comparison.

The monitoring cycle 2024 included counts of breeding pairs and nest success from 702 occupied stork nests. Our team collected the data via direct observations and with the assistance of villagers who served as citizen scientists. The nests are labelled with individual numbers, and villagers provide quick feedback on every unusual occasion, including the evidence of storks with contaminated plumage.

At each nest, we also recorded the number of contaminated storks, categorised into three levels based on how much smearing each had. Storks were “slightly contaminated” when the lower part of the neck and belly was smeared, having a pale greyish-buff colour,

“medium contaminated” when the neck, belly, and part of wings were smeared, having a dark greyish-buff, and “strongly contaminated,” when smearing covered almost the entire stork.

The collected data are stored in a Microsoft Access 2003 database (later transferred into Microsoft Office 2010) for further data analysis. Statistical analyses were carried out with Excel 2010 (MS Office 2010) and R program package. The analyses include the measurement of central tendencies and the calculation of statistically significant differences between variables. Considering that the variables were not normally distributed, the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test was used to determine whether there is statistical evidence that the average differences between observations for different years are significantly different from zero (Daniel & Cross 2013). Mapping was conducted with QGIS Desktop 3.30.2.

Parallel to the research, rescue works have been implemented, and although they do not directly relate to the conducted study, they have decreased the mortality of the storks.

Results

The results below demonstrate the distribution and scale of the storks' contamination before (2019-2021)

and after the intervention (2022-2023). Detailed information is presented in Tables 2-7.

In 2019-2021 (Tables 2-4), in observed 35 villages, the percentage of contaminated storks increased from 5% to 55%, inclining from 5% to 20% in 2019-2020 ($Z = -2.727$, d.f. = 34, $p = 0.006$) and from 20% to 55% in 2020-2021 ($Z = -4.542$, d.f. = 34, $p < 0.001$). The percentage of clean nestlings declined from 89% to 75% in 2019-2020 ($Z = -2.651$, d.f. = 34, $p = 0.008$) and

from 75% to 52% in 2020-2021 ($Z = -4.610$, d.f. = 34, $p < 0.001$) (Table 1, Figure 2). The percentage of strongly contaminated nestlings (out of all contaminated nestlings) changed from 18% to 5% in 2019-2020 ($Z = -1.095$, d.f. = 34, $p = 0.273$) and from 5% to 24% in 2021 ($Z = -3.061$, d.f. = 34, $p = 0.002$) (Figure 2). The distribution of contaminated storks spread geographically from five villages to 28 (Figure 3).

Table 1.

Change of the pattern of contamination of White Storks *Ciconia ciconia* in 35 villages of Ararat Plain of Armenia.

Year	Percentage of clean or contaminated nestlings compared to all nestlings			
	Clean	Slightly contaminated	Medium-level contaminated	Strongly contaminated
Before the intervention				
2019	981 89%	32 3%	71 6%	22 2%
2020	853 75%	239 21%	32 3%	14 1%
2021	587 52%	233 21%	175 16%	126 11%
After the intervention				
2022	918 71%	140 11%	178 14%	65 5%
2023	1175 75%	194 12%	170 11%	71 5%
2024	1099 81%	187 14%	93 7%	39 3%

Figure 2. Change of the pattern of contamination of White Storks *Ciconia ciconia* in 35 villages of Ararat Plain of Armenia. The blue line indicates the percentage of contaminated stork nestlings (out of the number of all stork nestlings); the red line indicates the percentage of strongly contaminated stork nestlings (out of the number of all contaminated stork nestlings); the green line indicates the percentage of clean nestlings.

In 2021-2024 (Tables 4-7), in the observed 35 villages, the percentage of contaminated storks decreased from 55% to 19%, almost three times, declining from 55% to 34% in 2021-2022 ($Z = -3.692$, d.f. = 34, $p < 0.001$), then to 22% in 2023 ($Z = -2.508$, d.f. = 34, $p = 0.012$), then to 19% in 2024 ($Z = -0.844$, d.f. = 34, $p =$

0.399). The percentage of clean nestlings increased from 52% to 81%, in 1.5 times, inclining from 52% to 71% in 2021-2022 ($Z = -3.552$, d.f. = 34, $p < 0.001$), then to 75% in 2023 ($Z = -2.554$, d.f. = 34, $p = 0.011$), and to 81% in 2024 ($Z = -1.328$, d.f. = 34, $p = 0.184$) (Table 1, Figure 2).

Figure 3. The pattern of White Storks' contamination in 2019-2024.

The percentage of strongly contaminated nestlings (out of all contaminated nestlings) decreased from 24% in 2021 to 17% in 2022 ($Z = -0.983$, d.f. = 34, $p = 0.348$), to 16% in 2023 ($Z = -0.131$, d.f. = 34, $p = 0.898$), and to 12% in 2024 ($Z = -0.256$, d.f. = 34, $p = 0.796$) (Figure 2). The distribution of the contaminated storks shrinks much slower, from 28 villages in 2021 to 23 villages in 2024 (Tables 4-7, Figure 3).

Discussion

From 2022 to 2024, the storks' contamination declined statistically significantly and consistently. The number of clean storks increased, and the number of strongly contaminated storks declined, too.

The observed decline of contaminated storks coincides with the beginning and consistent implementation of the strategy and action plan, jointly developed and introduced by the Ministry of Environment, Environ-

mental Inspection, BirdLinks Armenia NGO, and Protection of Endemic and Endangered Species NGO. Specifically, the strategy included several short-term urgent measures (Aghababayan *et al.* 2022) such as: (1) inventory by the Environmental Inspection of all the producers of fish, canned food, chips, etc., which can have fat or oil-containing waste; (2) enforcing all producers to provide annual reports on their waste, according to the legislation; (3) development of the annual cycle of comparison of the volume of the waste recorded in the annual report with the production volume to find possible violations (Aghababayan *et al.* 2022).

The Environmental Inspection identified over 300 such producers within the region of contaminated storks and implemented the planned inspections during 2022-2024, meanwhile broadcasting these steps among producers through its own Public Relations unit and with the help of the NGOs. At the same time, the Hazardous Substances and Waste Policy Department and Public Relations Division of the Ministry of Environment developed and distributed educational materials to popularise waste-related issues, obligations, and solutions for fish farmers and canned food producers. Therefore, the observed decline of the storks' contamination can be related to the improvement of waste-related behaviour of the fish farmers and producers of chips and canned food. Therefore, a continuation of the selected strategy and action plan is crucial for the complete elimination of the wetland and stork pollution issue.

The average number of strongly contaminated storks declined insignificantly. It appears that mainly the stork populations in the several villages contribute to that, e.g., Nizami (41%), Griboyedov (43%), Darakert (51%), and Norabats (55%). This can happen due to an overall decrease in the number of contaminated nestlings, where the proportion of the strongly contaminated ones becomes high even despite their total decline. Nevertheless, the existence of these hotspots requires further intensification of the inspection and education efforts in those settlements and around them.

Similar to previous years, there is no certainty about the agents smearing the storks. We continue relating to the fact that the storks' contamination declined after the beginning of the inspections (Aghababayan *et al.* 2022, 2024), which indirectly proves the hypothesis that the contamination sources are the fish producers (fatty internal organs of the fish thrown after the fish gutting) and chips and/or canned oil producers (wasted plant oil).

In previous years (Aghababayan *et al.* 2022, 2024), it was concluded that the country's environmental legislation is sufficient and requires enforcement, although can have crosscutting gaps with the territorial administration.

In response to the enforcement needs, the Environmental Inspection continues to examine all fish, chips, and canned food producers, forcing them to provide annual reports on waste (Aghababayan *et al.* 2024). Also, new decree (N 262-L) was issued by the Ministry of Environment on approval of the Fish-farms' Waste Management Guide, resulting in the development of the educational brochure "Fish-farms' Waste Management Guide" by the Hazardous Substances and Waste Policy

Department of the Ministry of Environment, its distribution through the series of seminars with the fish-farmers and canned food producers, as well as broadcasting the issue through the regular channels by the Public Relations Division of the Ministry, through the Association of Fish-farmers of Armenia (Aghababayan *et al.* 2024).

In response to the need to revise related legislation, the Ministry of Environment and the Ministry of Territorial Administration and Infrastructure proposed changes in the Law "On Waste Removal and Sanitation," specifically defining the regulations related to the management of biodegradable waste. Also, for the placement of other biological waste, the RA Code on Administrative Offenses (which will come into force on January 1, 2025) has established appropriate measures of responsibility for dumping waste outside of designated places and in unauthorized ways (Aghababayan *et al.* 2024).

The CSO sector (BirdLinks Armenia NGO and Protection of Endemic and Endangered Species NGO) continued broadcasting the issue and law enforcement through TV interviews and social media.

It appears that the observed decline of contaminated storks is directly related to the intensive joint efforts of the Ministry of Environment, Environmental Inspection, BirdLinks Armenia NGO, and Protection of Endemic and Endangered Species NGO described above. In this regard, the storks become very efficient indicators of the emerging issue and the efficacy of the undertaken efforts.

Conclusion

Given the observed positive dynamics in declining the contamination of the indicator species (White Stork), the current strategy and action plan developed and implemented by the state organisations and CSOs should be continued. Specifically, it is crucial to implement annual inspections of fish, chips, and canned food producers.

As long-term measures, it is essential to begin working on increasing punishments for violations of waste disposal rules and for harming the White Storks and their wetland habitats. Also, the development of recycling the remains of gutted fish and used plant oil should be started.

The monitoring of the White Storks should be continued to indicate the scale and severity of the pollution issue and the efficiency of the conservation efforts.

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Table 2.

Distribution of contaminated white storks among 35 surveyed villages in 2019.

#	Village	Number of nests	Conditional level of contamination of white storks in the nests				Number of nestlings	Number and % of contaminated storks	
			Clean	Slightly	Medium	Strong			
1	Geghanist	2	6	0	0	0	6	0	0%
2	Azatashen	2	5	0	0	0	5	0	0%
3	Khachpar	18	52	2	0	0	54	2	4%
4	Hayanist	9	24	3	0	0	27	3	11%
5	Howtashat	25	77	0	0	0	77	0	0%
6	Nizami	6	18	2	0	0	20	2	10%
7	Zorak	5	15	0	0	0	15	0	0%
8	Dashtavan	18	51	0	0	0	51	0	0%
9	Darakert	11	34	0	0	0	34	0	0%
10	Norabats	2	4	0	0	0	4	0	0%
11	Darbnik	4	11	0	0	0	11	0	0%
12	Ghukasavan	2	6	0	0	0	6	0	0%
13	Hovtashen	36	0	21	71	22	114	114	100%
14	Noramarg	4	8	4	0	0	12	4	33%
15	Yeraskhahun	41	118	0	0	0	118	0	0%
16	Yeghegnut	40	115	0	0	0	115	0	0%
17	Jrarat	8	22	0	0	0	22	0	0%
18	Metsamor	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
19	Haykashen	4	11	0	0	0	11	0	0%
20	Gay	8	26	0	0	0	26	0	0%
21	Lusagyugh	4	13	0	0	0	13	0	0%
22	Aknashen	3	9	0	0	0	9	0	0%
23	Griboyedov	8	22	0	0	0	22	0	0%
24	Aratashen	3	8	0	0	0	8	0	0%
25	Khoronk	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
26	Artimet	3	10	0	0	0	10	0	0%
27	Haytagh	2	8	0	0	0	8	0	0%
28	Mkhchyan	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
29	Dimitrov	4	14	0	0	0	14	0	0%
30	Sipanik	10	28	0	0	0	28	0	0%
31	Araksavan	16	48	0	0	0	48	0	0%
32	Pokr Vedi	12	37	0	0	0	37	0	0%
33	Lusarat	6	19	0	0	0	19	0	0%
34	Surenavan	24	74	0	0	0	74	0	0%
35	Armash	22	67	0	0	0	67	0	0%
	Totals	368	981	32	71	22	1106	125	

Table 3.

Distribution of contaminated white storks among 35 surveyed villages in 2020.

#	Village	Number of nests	Conditional level of contamination of white storks in the nests				Number of nest-lings	Number and % of contaminated storks	
			Clean	Slightly	Medium	Strong			
1	Geghanist	2	6	0	0	0	6	0	0%
2	Azataashen	2	5	0	0	0	5	0	0%
3	Khachpar	18	32	22	0	0	54	22	41%
4	Hayanist	9	20	11	0	0	31	11	35%
5	Howtashat	25	45	35	0	0	80	35	44%
6	Nizami	6	5	6	5	3	19	14	74%
7	Zorak	5	8	6	2	0	16	8	50%
8	Dashtavan	18	18	29	7	2	56	38	68%
9	Darakert	11	11	16	7	2	36	25	69%
10	Norabats	2	3	3	0	0	6	3	50%
11	Darbnik	4	9	5	0	0	14	5	36%
12	Ghukasavan	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
13	Hovtashen	35	59	40	5	7	111	52	47%
14	Noramarg	4	5	4	3	0	12	7	58%
15	Yeraskhahun	41	78	46	3	0	127	49	39%
16	Yeghegnut	40	121	0	0	0	121	0	0%
17	Jrarat	8	13	11	0	0	24	11	46%
18	Metsamor	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
19	Haykashen	4	11	0	0	0	11	0	0%
20	Gay	8	23	0	0	0	23	0	0%
21	Lusagyugh	4	8	3	0	0	11	3	27%
22	Aknashen	3	9	0	0	0	9	0	0%
23	Griboyedov	8	25	0	0	0	25	0	0%
24	Aratashen	3	10	0	0	0	10	0	0%
25	Khoronk	2	4	2	0	0	6	2	33%
26	Artimet	3	10	0	0	0	10	0	0%
27	Haytagh	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
28	Mkhchyan	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
29	Dimitrov	4	14	0	0	0	14	0	0%
30	Sipanik	10	29	0	0	0	29	0	0%
31	Araksavan	16	47	0	0	0	47	0	0%
32	Pokr Vedi	12	34	0	0	0	34	0	0%
33	Lusarat	6	22	0	0	0	22	0	0%
34	Surenavan	24	73	0	0	0	73	0	0%
35	Armash	22	68	0	0	0	68	0	0%
	Totals	367	853	239	32	14	1138	285	

Table 4.

Distribution of contaminated white storks among 35 surveyed villages in 2021.

#	Village	Number of nests	Conditional level of contamination of white storks in the nests				Number of nestlings	Number and % of contaminated Storks	
			Clean	Slightly	Medium	Strong			
1	Geghanist	2	3	0	2	0	5	2	40%
2	Azatashen	2	0	6	0	0	6	6	100%
3	Khachpar	18	6	12	17	21	56	50	89%
4	Hayanist	9	9	7	2	11	29	20	69%
5	Howtashat	25	23	28	25	0	76	53	70%
6	Nizami	6	0	8	6	4	18	18	100%
7	Zorak	5	0	2	4	9	15	15	100%
8	Dashtavan	18	0	9	19	26	54	54	100%
9	Darakert	11	0	12	8	13	33	33	100%
10	Norabats	2	0	4	2	0	6	6	100%
11	Darbnik	4	0	6	3	4	13	13	100%
12	Ghukasavan	2	2	4	0	0	6	4	67%
13	Hovtashen	36	32	39	21	16	108	76	70%
14	Noramarg	4	4	4	2	0	10	6	60%
15	Yeraskhahun	41	59	24	26	14	123	64	52%
16	Yeghegnut	40	118	0	0	0	118	0	0%
17	Jrrat	8	0	16	5	2	23	23	100%
18	Metsamor	2	4	3	0	0	7	3	43%
19	Haykashen	4	10	2	0	0	12	2	17%
20	Gay	8	15	7	3	0	25	10	40%
21	Lusagyugh	4	8	3	0	0	11	3	27%
22	Aknashen	3	7	2	1	0	10	3	30%
23	Griboyedov	8	18	5	0	0	27	5	22%
24	Aratashen	3	2	2	5	0	9	7	78%
25	Khoronk	2	4	3	0	0	7	3	43%
26	Artimet	3	2	5	2	0	9	7	78%
27	Haytagh	2	0	2	4	2	8	8	100%
28	Mkhchyan	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
29	Dimitrov	4	5	0	6	4	15	10	67%
30	Sipanik	10	31	0	0	0	31	0	0%
31	Araksavan	16	19	18	12	0	49	30	61%
32	Pokr Vedi	12	35	0	0	0	35	0	0%
33	Lusarat	6	20	0	0	0	20	0	0%
34	Surenavan	24	75	0	0	0	75	0	0%
35	Armash	22	69	0	0	0	69	0	0%
	Totals	368	587	233	175	126	1125	534	

Table 5.

Distribution of contaminated white storks among 35 surveyed villages in 2022.

#	Village	Number of nests	Conditional level of contamination of white storks in the nests				Number of nestlings	Number and % of contaminated storks	
			Clean	Slightly	Medium	Strong			
1	Geghanist	2	4	0	2	0	6	2	33%
2	Azatashen	2	3	4	0	0	7	4	57%
3	Khachpar	18	28	10	14	8	60	32	53%
4	Hayanist	12	31	0	3	0	34	3	9%
5	Howtashat	25	52	7	10	4	73	21	29%
6	Nizami	15	18	20	4	0	42	24	57%
7	Zorak	11	34	0	6	0	40	6	15%
8	Dashtavan	23	68	6	8	0	82	14	17%
9	Darakert	11	7	10	9	4	30	23	77%
10	Norabats	2	2	2	3	0	7	5	71%
11	Darbnik	6	22	0	0	0	22	0	0%
12	Ghukasavan	2	3	2	0	0	5	2	40%
13	Hovtashen	36	44	28	24	8	104	60	58%
14	Noramarg	4	5	3	2	0	10	5	50%
15	Yeraskhahun	60	154	0	22	18	194	40	21%
16	Yeghegnut	40	72	0	30	12	114	42	37%
17	Jrarat	8	4	10	4	5	23	19	83%
18	Metsamor	2	5	3	0	0	8	3	38%
19	Haykashen	4	8	3	0	0	11	3	27%
20	Gay	8	17	0	4	2	23	6	26%
21	Lusagyugh	4	9	1	0	0	10	1	10%
22	Aknashen	3	8	2	0	0	10	2	20%
23	Griboyedov	16	48	4	8	0	60	12	20%
24	Aratashen	3	3	2	4	0	9	6	67%
25	Khoronk	2	3	3	0	0	6	3	50%
26	Artimet	3	4	4	2	0	10	6	60%
27	Haytagh	2	2	2	2	2	8	6	75%
28	Mkhchyan	2	6	0	0	0	6	0	0%
29	Dimitrov	4	7	2	4	2	15	8	53%
30	Sipanik	10	28	0	4	0	32	4	13%
31	Araksavan	16	29	12	9	0	50	21	42%
32	Pokr Vedi	12	33	0	0	0	33	0	0%
33	Lusarat	6	18	0	0	0	18	0	0%
34	Surenavan	24	73	0	0	0	73	0	0%
35	Armash	22	66	0	0	0	66	0	0%
	Totals	420	918	140	178	65	1301	383	

Table 6.

Distribution of contaminated white storks among 35 surveyed villages in 2023.

#	Village	Number of nests	Conditional level of contamination of white storks in the nests				Number of nestlings	Number and % of contaminated storks	
			Clean	Slightly	Medium	Strong			
1	Geghanist	9	14	0	1	0	15	1	7%
2	Azatashen	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
3	Khachpar	12	28	2	4	0	34	6	18%
4	Hayanist	16	8	10	12	11	41	33	80%
5	Howtashat	25	58	10	8	0	76	18	24%
6	Nizami	24	37	5	11	9	62	25	40%
7	Zorak	12	18	0	6	9	33	15	45%
8	Dashtavan	36	33	5	37	17	92	59	64%
9	Darakert	9	16	8	2	0	26	10	38%
10	Norabats	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
11	Darbnik	13	22	1	2	9	34	12	35%
12	Ghukasavan	2	6	0	0	0	6	0	0%
13	Hovtashen	28	49	26	4	2	81	32	40%
14	Noramarg	4	9	2	0	0	11	2	18%
15	Yeraskhahun	39	65	9	10	1	85	20	24%
16	Yeghegnut	36	77	18	5	4	104	27	26%
17	Jrarat	8	15	4	2	0	21	6	29%
18	Metsamor	2	5	2	0	0	7	2	29%
19	Haykashen	4	8	2	0	0	10	2	20%
20	Gay	8	19	3	2	0	24	5	21%
21	Lusagyugh	15	37	2	0	0	39	2	5%
22	Aknashen	3	9	0	0	0	9	0	0%
23	Griboyedov	31	47	14	15	1	27	30	39%
24	Aratashen	10	21	0	5	1	27	6	22%
25	Khoronk	17	47	0	0	0	47	0	0%
26	Artimet	21	251	52	42	7	352	101	29%
27	Haytagh	2	5	2	0	0	7	2	29%
28	Mkhchyan	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
29	Dimitrov	4	10	2	2	0	14	4	29%
30	Sipanik	9	20	5	0	0	25	5	20%
31	Araksavan	15	28	8	0	0	36	8	22%
32	Pokr Vedi	12	36	0	0	0	36	0	0%
33	Lusarat	6	18	0	0	0	18	0	0%
34	Surenavan	24	71	0	0	0	71	0	0%
35	Armash	23	67	2	0	0	69	2	3%
	Totals	485	1175	194	170	71	1560	435	

Table 7.

Distribution of contaminated white storks among 35 surveyed villages in 2024.

#	Village	Number of nests	Conditional level of contamination of White Storks in the nests				Number of nest-lings	Number and % of contaminated Storks	
			Clean	Slightly	Medium	Strong			
1	Geghanist	12	24	1	0	0	25	1	4%
2	Azatashen	4	7	2	0	0	9	2	22%
3	Khachpar	13	20	11	0	0	31	11	35%
4	Hayanist	12	19	5	6	0	30	11	37%
5	Howtashat	53	65	15	17	5	102	37	36%
6	Nizami	36	48	13	12	8	81	33	41%
7	Zorak	7	8	2	1	2	13	5	38%
8	Dashtavan	36	47	13	9	2	71	24	34%
9	Darakert	22	19	11	5	4	39	20	51%
10	Norabats	35	27	17	12	4	60	33	55%
11	Darbnik	11	17	0	3	1	21	4	19%
12	Ghukasavan	19	28	6	0	0	34	6	18%
13	Hovtashen	43	58	22	0	0	80	22	28%
14	Noramarg	15	21	9	0	0	30	9	30%
15	Yeraskhahun	52	86	11	0	0	97	11	11%
16	Yeghegnut	36	71	9	2	0	82	11	13%
17	Jrarat	6	13	0	0	0	13	0	0%
18	Metsamor	2	5	0	0	0	5	0	0%
19	Haykashen	11	15	1	3	2	21	6	29%
20	Gay	21	34	7	4	6	51	17	33%
21	Lusagyugh	16	33	2	0	0	35	2	6%
22	Aknashen	3	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
23	Griboyedov	40	48	20	14	2	27	36	43%
24	Aratashen	13	21	0	5	1	27	6	22%
25	Khoronk	5	5	4	0	0	9	4	44%
26	Artimet	19	28	6	0	2	36	8	22%
27	Haytagh	1	2	0	0	0	2	0	0%
28	Mkhchyan	2	5	0	0	0	5	0	0%
29	Dimitrov	4	9	0	0	0	9	0	0%
30	Sipanik	9	19	0	0	0	19	0	0%
31	Araksavan	3	3	0	0	0	3	0	0%
32	Pokr Vedi	19	41	0	0	0	41	0	0%
33	Lusarat	6	15	0	0	0	15	0	0%
34	Surenavan	60	115	0	0	0	115	0	0%
35	Armash	56	116	0	0	0	116	0	0%
Totals		702	1099	187	93	39	1361	319	

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